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Understanding the flow of rock deformed under eclogite facies conditions is crucial to constraint the dynamics of a subducting slab. Prograde metamorphism during burial in a subduction zone proceeds across several lithologies, resulting in heterogeneous eclogitization and potentially different processes. In order to explore the expression of such a variety in terms of a deformative fabric, we have analyzed texture and shape fabric of eclogites and eclogitic orthogneisses from the Malpica-Tui unit (NW Spain). We explore the same rock volumes with TOF-neutron diffraction (HIPPO @ LANSCE) and synchrotron microtomography (SYRMEP @ Elettra). Orientation distribution functions were extracted after Rietveld refinement in MAUD and morphometric data (size, aspect ratio, orientation) were obtained after image processing with Fiji, Blob3D and MATLAB. Shape fabric reflects the macroscopic foliation and lineation and correlates with texture. Garnet fabric is particularly important because of the rheological implications of its mechanical behavior. Garnet shows little elongation in both samples, and texture is significant, what probably points to a relatively dry deformative environment, with diffusion-assisted dislocation. This eclogites could represent a rigidification stage in the subduction channel preserved during the exhumation at high-P and high-T documented in the Malpica-Tui unit during the Variscan orogeny.

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